

Design and Simulation of a Novel Nanoscale Vacuum Field Emission Transistor with a Vertical Channel and Finger Gate

Sharifi, Mohammad Javad. ^a, Kohani Khoshkbijari, Fatemeh ^{a*}

^aDepartment of Electrical Engineering, Shahid Beheshti University, Tehran, IRAN

*fa.kohani@iau.ac.ir

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Abstract: In this paper, the finger gate vertical vacuum channel field emission transistor in nanoscale regime is presented with the aim of decreasing gate leakage current in nanoscale vacuum devices. In a three-terminal proposed metal-based device with 43nm vertical channel and the ability to operate in air ambient, results indicate a suitable $101\mu\text{A}$ in $V_a=V_g=5\text{ V}$ while the leakage current is reduced 7 times in comparison with the conventional devices. The working frequency of the device is obtained $f_T=1.13\text{ THz}$ that shows significant performance in high-frequency applications. In this new device, other electrical characteristics such as I_{on}/I_{off} , V_{TH} , and g_m are assessed and their improvement is compared with conventional vacuum devices. The proposed structural modifications can provide a new level of ultra-fast low-power transistors for digital purposes.

Keywords: Nanoscale transistor with vacuum channel, field emission, finger gate, electrical characteristics.

1. INTRODUCTION

Nanoscale field emission devices have garnered significant attention due to their advantages over conventional semiconductor devices. These advantages include faster switching speeds, performance that is independent of temperature, the ability to operate in radiation-rich environments, and the elimination of the need for vacuum packaging [1].

Another notable feature of field emission devices with channel lengths shorter than 100 nm is their capability to function at atmospheric pressure without requiring vacuum encapsulation. Various structures, including sharp-tip and flat configurations, have been proposed for nanoscale vacuum field emission devices [2][3]. Recent studies have shown that gate control over the channel in these devices is inadequate, necessitating higher voltages to achieve acceptable on-state currents. The most recent configuration proposed involves vertical channel structures, which not only require lower operating voltages compared to planar structures but also demonstrate performance characteristics similar to those of solid-state transistors [4].

However, the presence of gate leakage current in these structures poses a significant limitation on device performance. In response to this challenge, this paper introduces a novel design for a vacuum channel field emission transistor with a finger gate (FGVFET). This design features a specialized gate geometry aimed at minimizing leakage current and improving the electrical characteristics of nanoscale vacuum channel devices.

2. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Figure 1-a presents the schematic of the designed device. In this configuration, the vacuum channel has a length of 100 nm and a width of 50 nm. The distance between the anode and cathode is approximately set to match the average free path of electrons in a vacuum. Rather than employing a simple integrated gate, a design featuring separate, symmetrical finger gates has been implemented to minimize the gate's cross-sectional area. This modification allows for a thorough examination of its effects on gate leakage current and other electrical characteristics.

To evaluate the performance of the vertical channel vacuum transistor, simulations were conducted using CST Multiphysics software.

Figure 1a) Schematic of the designed vacuum channel field emission transistor with a finger gate. Figure 1b) Anode current characteristic curve as a function of anode voltage for various gate voltages.

The results reveal that the gate leakage current in the FGVFET device, measured at $I_g = 6.087 \times 10^{-9}$ A, has decreased by approximately 86% compared to the VFET structure, which exhibits a leakage current of $I_g = 4.246 \times 10^{-8}$ A. This significant reduction is attributed to the smaller gate dimensions, which lead to less electron absorption by the gate.

The I-V characteristic curve of the device, illustrated in Figure 1-b, clearly delineates three distinct regions: cutoff, linear, and saturation, akin to those observed in conventional MOSFET devices.

Table 1 compares the electrical characteristics of the proposed FGVFET with those from previous studies in the realm of nanoscale vacuum devices. Remarkably, a transconductance (g_m) of $53 \mu S$ was achieved at $V_a = 5V$ and $V_g = 5V$, significantly surpassing values reported in earlier research. The calculated transition frequency (f_T) for the FGVFET is 1.13THz, approximately 2.5 times greater than that of flat structures [2]. This highlights the advantages of employing finger gate structures in high-speed and digital applications. Additionally, the I_{on}/I_{off} ratio in the FGVFET falls within the typical range for conventional MOSFETs, indicating a marked improvement over other VFET configurations.

Table 1: Comparison of the electrical characteristics of the FGVFET device with previous studies.

	FGVFET	Ref [2]	Ref [6]	Ref [5]	Ref [3]	Ref [1]
Channel Length	35	150	35	50	100	20
$V_{TH}(V)$	0.55	10	36	2	10	0.5
$C_{ga}(aF)$	7.42	0.069	-	-	-	-
$g_m(\mu S)$	53	0.2	-	34	-	2
$f_T(THz)$	1.13	0.46	-	-	-	-
I_{on}/I_{off}	1.89×10^6	1×10^6	321.85	1×10^6	1×10^5	500

3. CONCLUSION

This paper presents a finger gate vertical vacuum channel field emission transistor aimed at reducing gate leakage current in nanoscale vacuum devices. The device, with a 43 nm vertical channel, achieves $101 \mu A$ at $V_a = V_g = 5V$ and reduces leakage current by seven times compared to conventional devices. With a working frequency (f_T) of 1.13 THz and improved electrical characteristics like I_{on}/I_{off} , V_{TH} , and g_m , this device shows significant potential for ultra-fast, low-power digital applications.

4. REFERENCES

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